

CONTENT OF GRAMMATICAL CATEGORIES IN TWO LANGUAGES AND TYPOLOGY OF PARTS OF SPEECH.

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Abstract. The article gives us information about some categories of Russian language and compare them with English ones. The case category, the number category and the gender category is described and compared. It is almost generally accepted that there is a class of nouns that have two case forms, the Nominative and the possessive, which are formed by the morpheme's. These are the class of animate nouns and nouns of the semantic field 'time'. So, for example, in Finnish, where the number of cases of nouns is 14, there are very few prepositions. In English, on the other hand, with its limited system of cases, the number of prepositions is considerable. The category of certainty - indefiniteness. In many western European languages and some oriental languages, the noun system is characterised by definiteness - indefiniteness. This noun category has its own morphological form. Most often it is expressed by an article, as in English, German and French.

Keyword: The case category, the number category and the gender category, typology of parts of speech and content of grammatical categories, unity of the meaning, form of expression.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИХ КАТЕГОРИЙ В ДВУХ ЯЗЫКАХ И ТИПОЛОГИЯ ЧАСТЕЙ РЕЧИ.

Аннотация. В статье даются сведения о некоторых категориях русского языка и проводится сравнение их с английскими. Описаны и сопоставлены падежная категория, числовая категория и гендерная категория. Почти общепринято, что существует класс существительных, которые имеют две падежные формы: именительный и притяжательный падеж, образованные морфемой 's. Это класс одушевленных существительных и существительных семантического поля «время». Так, например, в финском языке, где число падежей существительных 14, предлогов очень мало. Напротив, в английском языке с его ограниченной системой падежей количество предлогов значительно. Категория определенности – неопределенность. Во многих западноевропейских языках и некоторых восточных языках именной системе свойственна определенность – неопределенность. Данная категория существительных имеет свою морфологическую форму. Чаще всего оно выражается артиклем, как в английском, немецком и французском языках.

Ключевое слово: Падежная категория, числительная категория и родовая категория, типология частей речи и содержание грамматических категорий, единство значения, форма выражения.

Introduction. The case category The category of case is understood as a grammatical category that represents the unity of the meaning of the relation of the indicated object to other objects, actions, features and the means of its material, linguistic expression. The real form of expression of this category is the case form, or form of case, which is a morpheme consisting of a

certain sound row, which together with the root morpheme gives a certain content to a word. The aggregate of the case forms, which form a definite system of change, constitutes the declension. Main part The number of declension varies in different languages, and this fact may be regarded as one of the criteria for the typological characterisation of the morphological system of a given language, as the presence or absence of declension is connected with the presence, absence or weak development of prepositions. So, for example, in Finnish, where the number of cases of nouns is 14, there are very few prepositions. In English, on the other hand, with its limited system of cases, the number of prepositions is considerable. There are languages where the case system in the noun does not exist at all, as in Bulgarian, Italian and French.

In the Russian language the case category is represented by six cases - *именительный, родительный, дательный, винительный, творительный и предложный*. (nominative, genitive, dative, accusative, vocative and prepositional.) When we consider the meaning of each individual case as a special grammatical category, we see that it has a complex character and consists of a number of smaller consciousnesses which, however, cannot be further decomposed. For instance, as one of these may be called objecthood, because the category of case is a characteristic of nouns denoting objects and phenomena. Another may be that the gender of a noun is assigned to a particular grammatical gender. The third inflection is the sense of number, singular or plural. The fourth signification is that it is animate or inanimate, and expresses itself in one form or another, etc. Following Professor E.I. Shendels, we call these conceptions *sema*. The term *sema* is thus understood as a minimal, further indivisible element of grammatical meaning. In Russian the category of case is characterised by the presence of the following *semes*: subjectness, gender, number, animate/inanimate. Apart from the stem of the case in general, each of the cases in The Russian language has a number of its own peculiar terms. So, for example, the Accusative Case is characterised by the *seme* 'direction of action'. The genitive case is characterised by a *seme* "belonging", etc.

The category of case in English has been a matter of debate to date. Depending on the author's approach to this problem, different numbers of cases have been assigned to the English language. M. Deitschbein, who understood case as a combination of a preposition and a noun in the initial form, thought there were four cases in English: nominative, genitive, dative and accusative. However, such an interpretation of the problem of case is fundamentally wrong, because a case is a word-form which has an appropriate case morpheme, in the case of English - 's. It is almost generally accepted that there is a class of nouns that have two case forms, the Nominative and the possessive, which are formed by the morpheme 's. These are the class of animate nouns and nouns of the semantic field 'time'. Thus, from the point of view of the typological characterisation of the case category in nouns, we can note that in English all nouns are divided into two classes: words denoting inanimate objects, which have no case category, and words denoting animate objects and time, which have two cases - general and possessive. The possessive case has the following: objectivity, animate, possessive, subjective and objective.

According to A. M. Mukhin's point of view, the case category no longer exists in the noun system of modern English. It ceased to exist as early as the Middle English period. The morpheme - es > 's preserved from the Old English period is nothing else but a possessive suffix, which is agglutinative by virtue of its unambiguity (possessive suffix) and its capacity to attach to the root

morpheme without modifying it. If we accept this point of view as true, which corresponds to the present state of the noun system in English, then we should conclude that the case category in the noun system does not actually exist. At the same time, a new grammatical category has emerged in the system of the name - the category of possessive, which has its material expression in the form of the agglutinative morpheme's. The case category is represented in the English pronoun system by two cases, the nominative and the object case, with the main semas of subject, number and direction. Category of number. In both English and Russian there is the grammatical category of number. This category expresses quantitative relations existing in reality, reflected in the minds of speakers of a given language and having morphological expression in the corresponding forms of language. The category of number is expressed differently in individual languages. For example, there are languages in which the category of number is expressed not only in plural, but also in dual and triple; such are some Papuan languages on the island of New Guinea. In the ancient Indo-European languages - Sanskrit, Ancient Greek, Ancient Germanic - the number category was represented by three numbers: singular, dual and plural. The category of number, as reflecting quantitative relations between real objects, is naturally attached to a noun.

In Russian and in English the category of number is represented by the semes of singularity and plurality, which are expressed in singular and plural forms. The gender category. The great majority of modern Indo-European languages are characterised by a peculiar lexical-grammatical category of gender. It is manifested in the ability of nouns to assimilate to themselves in the expression of grammatical meanings the forms of their dependent words - adjectives, pronouns, etc. The category of grammatical gender - masculine, feminine, neuter - was once peculiar to Old English nouns. However, historical development of the morphological structure of the English language led to the fact that the category of grammatical gender deprived of morphological means of expression ceased to exist. It is replaced by a new category, which Prof. V.N. Yartseva called the category of activity - passive. The essence of this new grammatical category consists in distinguishing two classes of words in the system of nouns: active nouns and passive nouns. The category of certainty - indefiniteness. In many western European languages and some oriental languages, the noun system is characterised by definiteness - indefiniteness. This noun category has its own morphological form. Most often it is expressed by an article, as in English, German and French. In other cases, it may be expressed in the form of affixes, so-called postpositional articles, morphemes added to the end of the noun word, as in Bulgarian, Romanian and Scandinavian languages.

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